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Experimental

Preparation of complexes: $M(\text{NO}_2-\text{Bz})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Cu}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}, \text{Cd}^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $n=0$ but 2 in case of Ni^{2+}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal acetate was treated with hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (1:2.5 molar ratio) and pH was raised to 7-8 by adding a few drops of dilute ammonia when the neutral complex separated. The product was digested on a steam bath for about half an hour, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at $\sim 100^\circ$ in an air oven.

$M(\text{NO}_2-\text{BzH})_2 \cdot X_2$, ($M = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $X = \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^-): Methanolic (or acetone) solution of metal halide (0.005 mole in 50 ml) was treated with stoichiometric proportion of ligand dissolved in the same solvent. From resulting solution, the dihalo complexes separated gradually. The product was filtered, washed with cold methanol and dried in air. The determination of magnetic moment values, solid reflectance and ir spectra of the complexes were made as reported earlier^{2,3}.

Results and Discussion

The neutral bis ligated complexes $M(\text{NO}_2-\text{Bz})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are insoluble in water and organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, chloroform, acetone etc., indicating their polymeric nature. Excepting Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} , the dihalo or other acidic complexes of other common metals like $\text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}, \text{Fe}^{2+}, \text{Mn}^{2+}, \text{VO}^{2+}$ etc. could not be isolated in solid state, similar to benzimidazole^{5,6} and alkyl benzimidazole^{7,8}, probably due to weak metal-ligand bonding caused by low electron density on imidazole nitrogen of NO_2-BzH molecule.

The dihalo complexes $M(\text{NO}_2-\text{BzH})_2 \cdot X_2$ ($M = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+}) are slightly soluble in ethanol, dioxane, dinso and DMF. The molar conductance values of complexes in DMF solution are negligible (Λ_M 8-15 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) indicating the coordination of halogen atoms in these complexes.

Zn(II) , Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are diamagnetic and do not display electronic absorption band in the visible region. On the basis of stoichiometry, four coordinated tetrahedral structure is tentatively suggested for Zn(II) , Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes since tetrahedral geometry is the more preferred geometry for these metal ions⁹.

The colour, magnetic moment value (μ_{eff} 4.71 B.M.) and reflectance spectrum of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2-\text{Bz})_2$ decidedly indicate its pseudotetrahedral structure^{10,11}. A strong band at 18020 cm^{-1} is assigned ${}^4\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition and a shoulder at $18,850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to splitting of ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ term under the influence of spin-orbit coupling in tetrahedral field¹².

$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_2-\text{Bz})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ displays magnetic moment value, ca 2.96 B.M., similar to octahedral or distorted octahedral nickel(II) ions¹³. The diffused reflectance spectrum in the region 28,500-10,000 cm^{-1} exhibits a weak and broad band at

Complexes of 5-Nitrobenzimidazole with Some Metal Ions

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COMPLEXES of various transition metal ions with benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles have been reported¹⁻⁶. 5-Nitrobenzimidazole (NO_2-BzH) contains an electron withdrawing NO_2 group capable of reducing electron density at donor benzimidazole nitrogens through hyperconjugation. It is, therefore, expected that donor ability of benzimidazole nucleus will be affected appreciably. In

the present note, the preparation and characterisation of Ni(II) , Co(II) , Zn(II) , Cu(II) , Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes with NO_2-BzH are reported. The effect of NO_2 substitution on donor ability of benzimidazole nucleus is also discussed.

TABLE-1

Complex (LH=NO ₂ - BzH)	Colour	% Metal		% Nitrogen	μ_{eff} (B.M.) (at 304 K)	Spectral band position (cm ⁻¹)
		Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.)			
CoL ₂	Pink	15.21 (15.38)	21.61 (21.94)	4.71	18850 sh, 18020 s	
CuL ₂	Greenish yellow	16.24 (16.38)	21.21 (21.61)	1.88	16010-14760 br	
NiL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	Yellowish green	13.81 (14.01)	20.13 (20.06)	2.96	25370 sh, 15380 w	
ZnL ₂	Cream	17.01 (16.78)	21.41 (21.58)	Dia.	-	
CdL ₂	Cream	25.46 (25.75)	19.42 (19.25)	Dia.	-	
HgL ₂	Cream	37.81 (38.23)	16.31 (16.02)	Dia.	-	
Cu(LH) ₂ Cl ₂	Bluish green	13.81 (13.79)	18.11 (18.24)	1.92	15150-13500 br	
Cu(LH) ₂ Br ₂	Brown	11.71 (11.56)	15.07 (15.23)	1.84	14280-12500 br	
Hg(LH) ₂ Cl ₂	Cream yellow	33.21 (33.58)	14.21 (14.06)	Dia.	-	
Hg(LH) ₂ Br ₂	Cream yellow	29.66 (29.23)	12.11 (12.41)	Dia.	-	

Results of halogen analyses in complexes correspond with the required values.

13,380 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at 25,370 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) and ³A_{2g} → ³A_{1g} (P) transitions, respectively¹⁴. From the relations of different ligand field parameters with the energies of ν_2 and ν_3 transitions the values of 10 Dq and B have been calculated and are found to be 9523 and 810 cm⁻¹, respectively¹⁵.

Copper(II) complexes display magnetic moment values between 1.84 and 1.92 B.M. indicating that these complexes are magnetically dilute¹⁶. The reflectance spectrum of Cu(NO₂-Bz)₂ displays a broad and weak band at 16,130-14,720 cm⁻¹ assignable to combination of ³B_{2g} → ³B_{1g} plus ³B_{2g} → ³A_{1g} transitions in distorted octahedral field¹⁷. The ligand field bands in dihalo complexes CuL₂X₂ (L=NO₂-BzH and X=Cl or Br) are observed at low energy (15,150-12,500 cm⁻¹) and are assymmetric in nature. The occurrence of d-d transition at low energy and assymmetric nature of spectral band indicate that tetragonal distortion is more in dihalo complexes than that of Cu(NO₂-Bz)₂.

The ir spectrum of ligand displays (N-H) stretching band at 3258 cm⁻¹ which disappears in its neutral complexes M(NO₂-Bz)₂ (M=Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺ or Hg²⁺) indicating that (N-H) proton has been deprotonated in its complexes. The diaquo complex [Ni(NO₂-Bz)₂(H₂O)₂] displays a broad and medium band at 3300-3450 and a shoulder at 1630 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of water molecules in the complexes. The (N-H) stretching band of NO₂-BzH is not affected appreciably in its dihalo complexes indicating that NH nitrogen is not involved in bonding. The (C=N) stretch of the ligand is found at 1593 cm⁻¹ which is observed at 1600 ± 5 cm⁻¹ in its complexes suggesting involvement of (C=N) nitrogen in bond

formation¹⁸. Besides (C=N) stretch the ligand and its complexes display a number of bands in 6-16 μ region due to various modes of NO₂, (N-H), (C-N) and phenyl ring vibrations. The prominent bands of ligand and its complexes are observed at 1533 ± 2, 1490 ± 3, 1468 ± 5, 1405 ± 2, 1340 ± 2, 1300 ± 2, 1255 ± 3, 1220 ± 3, 1120 ± 1, 1065 ± 3, 950 ± 10, 870 ± 5, 830 ± 1, 815 ± 3, 755 ± 1, 730 ± 2, 670 ± 2 and 640 ± 5 cm⁻¹. The ir spectra of complexes could not be recorded in far ir region and nothing could be suggested about (M-N) vibrations.

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Complexes of Some Platinum Metals with 4-Amino-3,5-Dimercapto-1,2,4-Triazole

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In a previous communication¹ the complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H_2AMT) were reported. In the present communication we are reporting the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Ru(II), Rh(III), Pd(II) and Pt(II) with H_2AMT .

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: $M(HAMT)_2$, ($M = Pd^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of metal chloride (1.0%, ~50 ml) was treated with pyridine dropwise to get a light yellow solution of $[M(Py)_4]Cl_2$. The resulting solution of tetrapyridino complex was refluxed on a steam bath with an excess of ligand (1 : 2.5 molar ratio) in ethanolic solution when almost insoluble precipitate of the bis chelated complex separated out. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried in air (yield almost quantitative).

[Ru($HAMT$)₂]: An ethanolic solution of ruthenium(II) chloride² (1.0%, 50 ml) was refluxed with an excess of ligand (1 : 2.5 molar ratio) for half an hour when a dark green precipitate began to separate slowly. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air. Yield about 70–80%.

[Rh($HAMT$)₂.Cl.H₂O]: An ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium(III) chloride (2.0%, 50 ml) was refluxed with excess of ligand on a steam bath by adjusting pH to 2-3 with dilute hydrochloric acid for about 1 hr. The chloro complex $[Rh(HAMT)_2.Cl.H_2O]$ separated as brick red precipitate. The product was collected on a filter, washed with ethanol and dried as usual.

[Rh₂(AMT)₃]: The complex was obtained as insoluble orange red precipitate, when an ethanolic solution of hydrated rhodium(III) chloride (pH 5-6) was refluxed with 1 : 2 molar ratio of ligand on a steam bath for about 1 hr.

The ligand was prepared as reported earlier¹. The platinum metal chlorides were obtained from Johnson and Mathey Ltd.

The analytical results and electronic reflectance or absorption bands of complexes with their tentative assignments are shown in Table 1.

Magnetic susceptibilities and electronic spectra of the complexes were measured as reported earlier¹. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr disc on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of complexes (Table 1) show that 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole (A) forms complexes with tautomeric forms B and C.

The attempt to prepare Ru(III) and Pt(IV) complexes was unsuccessful since they were reduced by the ligand to Ru(II) and Pt(II) respectively. The complexes of $HAMT^-$ as well as AMT^{2-} are almost soluble in ethanol and water but are sparingly soluble in DMF or dioxane. The poor solubility of the complexes indicates their polymeric nature. The complexes are diamagnetic, indicating four coordinated square planar structure for Pd(II) and Pt(II) while octahedral for Rh(III) and Ru(II) in these complexes. The solid reflectance spectrum of $Rh(HAMT)_2.Cl.H_2O$ displays shoulders near 470 nm and 340 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g} + CT$ transitions (Table 1) in octahedral environment of rhodium(III) ions^{3,4}. The reflectance spectrum of $Ru(HAMT)_2$ displays a broad and weak band near 570-580 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transition, similar to hexa-coordinated Ru(II) complexes^{5,6}. The other d-d transition of Ru(II) complex could not be observed due to strong charge transfer absorption. In solid state $[Pd(HAMT)_2]$ shows a shoulder near 500 nm, while in solution it shows a number of bands between 350 and 200 nm (Table 1) attributable to ligand field and charge transfer bands⁷. Reflectance spectrum of $[Pt(HAMT)_2]$ displays a shoulder near 400 nm assignable to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transition⁷ in square planar field.

The assignment of ir spectral bands of H_2AMT and its complexes has been reported previously¹. In the present investigation it is found that NH_2 and NH stretching vibrations of the ligand in the complexes are not well resolved, rather it is observed as a broad and medium band near $3130 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The NH_2 deformation vibrations (Table 2) of ligand are also shifted to higher frequencies suggesting the bonding of NH_2 nitrogen in these complexes. The thioamide bands (I to IV) of ligand are affected appreciably in complexes and are observed as broad and medium to weak bands in AMT^{2-} complexes, and as well resolved and